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MANAGING EDUCATION FOR INNOVATION AND SECURITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUB-SHARA AFRICA: POLICY FORMULATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OPTION

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Abstract

The attraction of the paper is on the expectation of stakeholders (learners, teachers, accounting heads of schools, parents, ministry of education officials, quality assurance officials from Universal Basic Education Board from the education sector to manage education for innovation and security in the development of the sector in Sub-Sahara Africa, most especially in Nigeria. This development is for them to be enhanced with the option of the right policy formulation and implementation approaches. This evolved because of the fact that education, the global instrument for the growth of the entire citizenry for effective and efficient performance on educational administration job' characteristics, and also to grow the individual, community and overall development of every nation involved. This paper, therefore, examined the process of managing education for innovation and security for overall school administration and management in the development of education industry. The paper specifically addressed the following sub-themes: the concept of managing education for innovation and security job' characteristics development; education policies, formulation and implementation blueprint; the concept of managing education for security; innovative education programme in the education policy formulation for national development; education policy development progression in Nigeria; challenges of managing education for innovation and security; and the 6-3-3-4, 9-3-4, and 1-6-3-3-4 and Universal Basic Education policy structures of education. The paper concluded and recommended among others, that the federal, state and local government education authorities in the 774 local government areas of Nigeria as part of sub-Sahara African countries should get re-think pattern of implementing educational programmes according to the dictate of the existing policy contents. For instance, give consideration to innovation and security education of required and necessary education resources provision for all in the process of implementation

Keywords: Innovation and Security; Development; policy formulation; policy implementation; and Educational Administration.

Introduction

Education portends the global instrument for the growth of the entire citizenry to achieve effective and efficient performance in the individual, community and overall development and advancement of every nation involved. It is meant for the promotion of economy and development of sovereignty of Nigeria and Nigerians. It is stipulated in Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, (2014), education is a weapon per se for social and economic development of citizens. Education also develops in individuals those values which make them good citizens with attributes of honesty, selflessness, tolerance, dedication, hard works and personal integrity, all of which provide the rich resources from which good leadership potential is built after graduation from schools (Anyawu, 2019).

On this note, government has invested so much funds in it at the federal, state and local government educational levels. The complexity of the school population is high at the basic, post-basic and tertiary institutions of educational administration and management. Managing schools for innovation and security educational development for goal attainment is expected to be planned, organized, coordinated, directed, and budgeted for very well (Harbau & Egbebi, 2019).

The planning and implementation stages of school curriculum ought to be monitored for the training of the younger generation to balance justification for balanced education for the promotion of teacher quality and learners' access and quality education service delivery, and implementation of drafted curriculum to include where necessarily concerned stakeholders (learners, teachers, accounting heads of schools, parents, ministry of education officials, quality assurance officials from Universal Basic Education Board etc.) during planning stage till completion in line with the nature of the environment.

From 1842 till today, several education policies were previously formulated and implemented in the systems of educational administration and management at different times in the sector in Nigeria. The colonial masters from Europe came with an education policy that favour their own continent (Amusan, 2010). Innovation usually comes to life through interpretation of policy statements and interactions between players of curriculum formulators and implementers through step by steps ideas as generated in the process. Such players are expected to identify areas that could lead to innovative educational practices. This may develop into the protection of security education.

Innovation doesn't occur in a vacuum, but requires open interactions between systems and their environments, for instance, the school and its society/community people (OECD, 2016). This is also usually much the case for education sector. Schools cannot be left alone to make the transformation process to be difficult but need support of policies, and also from other actors and stakeholders such as parents, community leaders, scholars, non-governmental organization among others are supposedly the agents of innovative and security education out of the systems. In recent years, the emergent education industry has taken on a very important role bringing innovation that probably may lead to security education in schools and colleges from basic to tertiary education levels.

In the African traditional setting, people formulated an informal policy of school governance without writing. For Islamic education, it was reading and writing of Arabic letters and lessons of the holy Quran for better living standards was promoted in the Islamic and Arabic Education entrenchment (Arikehuyo, 2016). The Christian/Western education surfaced at its time and season as well to facilitate evangelism of the gospel of Jesus Christ and to promote

trading activities of the white men in Africa and most especially in Nigeria. With it, the idea of reading, writing and arithmetic (3 Rs.) systems of education was fashioned (Egbebi, 2019). The white-collar jobs were given to people and they worked as interpreters, clerks among others (Amusan, 2010). All these put together promoted foreign education policy

The era of taking over schools by the colonial government that employed series of ordinances regarded as policies of educational administration came on board: the Luggard constitution of 1900; Clifford constitution of 1946; Macpherson constitution of 1951 among others (Amusan, 2010). The dispensation of Nigeria government took over the educational administration developed at a time in retrospect when the first Premier of Western region in person of Chie Obafemi Awolowo launched the free education systems of educational administration in the year 1955; Eastern regional government launched its own in 1957 and Northern region in 1959 respectively (Amusan, 2010),

Challenges identified with the series of educational administration policies whether formal or informal led to the 1969 national policy of education conference. The first edition of education policy was published in the year 1977; reprinted 1981, 1998, fourth edition in 2004; fifth edition 2007; sixth edition first printed in 2013 and finally reprinted in 2014 (FRN, 2014). This is done to arrive at a master template to administer education sector plan for innovation and security education for development in sub-Saharan Africa. From those stages of unique educational development up till present, questions that have to do with innovation and security for development ought to be asked. This paper, therefore, addressed the process of managing education for innovation and security for the right development in sub-Saharan Africa and most especially Nigeria.

The concept of Managing Education for Innovation characteristics of Development

Managing education for innovation connotes the formulation and implementation of contents of education policy to pin-point innovative statements that could bring about innovation in the systems, not just of new ideas, knowledge, and practices. Innovation ought to improve the ideas, knowledge into as got in the policy and then put into practice enhancement of teaching and learning process for best attainment of the reason for the school establishment (Kostoff, 2003; Mitchell, 2003). The expected ultimate attraction is to bring improvement in the methods of teaching and learners' academic performance, cost efficiency, equity or public satisfaction (Kostoff, 2003; Mitchell, 200). Innovation is thus different from reform or change, which do not necessarily mean the application of something new, nor does it imply the application of improved ideas or knowledge (King & Anderson, 2002). Huerta Melchor (2008) suggested that reform is only one way of arriving at the right changes in the system; it implies a special approach to problem-solving through reform of the systems.

At some point in time, changes in school organisations are key parts of reform for the innovation needed, but other reforms may produce little or no change. Change may be an intended or unintended phenomenon, whereas reform to produce innovation is structured and programmed as it has been experienced in the stages of educational administration and management in Nigeria. This cropped up right away from the traditional era to the present dispensation in the systems of the education sector. Reforms can occur in political, economic, social and administrative domains and contain ideas about problems and solutions and are typically understood as initiatives driven from the top of a system or organization. This will develop in school administration when stakeholders in their strengths were able to identify elements of innovation in the existing educational policy.

They are not expected to be reviewing, re-editing and re-publishing education policy over and over.

In line with innovation comes from the Oslo Manual (OECD/Eurostat, 2005), it is defined as “the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, some new instructional management strategies, or a new organisational method in school business practices, workplace organisation or external relations”. This could be attributed to the ideas incorporated in the national policy on education on how schools should be administered around human and non-human resources for innovation and security attainment. In this definition, implementation refers to the introduction of a school product to the sector, or the actual use of processes, various methods of teaching by the classroom managers to achieve objectives easily with results.

Education systems are running up against very serious problems which, if left untouched, could result in serious risks not only for education itself but also for future economic growth, social progress and the well-being of stakeholders. According to OECD (2016), since the mid-20th century, education systems have expanded enormously and human populations have never been more highly educated than today. Emerging economies and developing countries are now also relentlessly expanding their education systems, seeing education as an indispensable ingredient of innovation for modernization and progress. Indeed, the benefits to individuals and societies remain very impressive. Yet, although many policy makers may consider the continued expansion in numbers as the best route forward.

The 1969 education conference in Nigeria is an advance of innovation to get the best master plan to administer education systems at the three levels of educational administration nationwide. UPE in 1976 came as an innovation to improve practice and standards in primary education systems; Universal Basic Education was launched by Chief Olusegun Obasanjo in 1990 and implementation of such began in the year 2000 to promote innovation of access, equity and fair play for all children of school going age to be in the classroom. This development supported the 6-3-3-4 programme of education. Learners are expected to spend six years in primary school, three years in junior secondary schools; three years in senior secondary schools and finally four years in tertiary institutions. Like Universities, other levels of tertiary institutions like colleges of education, polytechnics and many more fall under the last four years of educational pursuit in the ranking.

Education Policies and Formulation and Implementation Blueprint

Education policies hosted this programme of education in place. National policy on education. The first edition of education policy was published in the year 1977; reprinted 1981, 1998, fourth edition in 2004; fifth edition 2007; sixth edition first printed 2013 and finally reprinted in 2014 (FRN, 2014). It may be seen as an instrument of innovation for best educational implementation package. During the formulation stages of development, steps for implementation were so stated. Human and materials resources to be provided are stipulated for the smooth running of stages of educational development and growth in basic, post-basic and tertiary institutions. At implementation stage, the goal of managing education for innovation is in most cases thwarted by players. The major challenge of education has to do with productivity and efficiency.

National Policy of Education Versus Innovation in Retrospect

Prior to the 1969 education policy formulation and implementation and other years of review of the policy in Nigeria as stipulated earlier, the 6-5-4 education programme in

schools did not allow innovation of administering school programme of studies in line with our culture in the tropical region that favours agricultural practice and vocational education that may lead to self-reliance and hands-on learning but allow book knowledge alone. Then, the innovation there present in it is for the students to get white-collar jobs in the long run (Egbebi, 2019). As a matter of fact, efficiency signifies the balance between resources invested in education and the outcomes in terms of students' performance and equity.

Over the past years, ever more resources have been invested in education. Instead, in most countries the percentage of top performers has declined and while the PISA data show some progress in equity, huge gaps are still in equality of opportunity and education outcomes between various social groups (OECD, 2013). The innovation for security education expected from the programme of studies then refused to yield the appropriate results despite the fact funds have been disbursed towards school resources. Ibraheem., Umar., and Ajoke (2013) noted in the year 1983, that the innovation brought by the Southwest governors by bringing education resources to promote self-reliance and vocational education did not yield results because all the teachers used the equipment procured and bought were not trained. In the long run, such educational resources melted in the labouratories and buildings where they were stored. Innovations that can sustain security education are embedded in the formulated policy to guide educational administration but the ability of the stakeholders to identify the tune of innovation in the policy is the key factor to bring about such.

Furthermore, if all pupils right away from primary school to university level will be encouraged to practice agriculture, there will be more food for export and local consumption, if not for exportation. Some questions rightly come to mind here: do teachers have the methodology for practical agriculture? Are there landed properties to implement the skills gotten by the teachers if there is any knowledge, skill and cognate experience on agricultural training programme? School leavers and graduates from tertiary institutions possess just skills for white-collar jobs as stipulated by researchers (Amusan, 2010). Most students find it difficult to show skills in the world of work on the courses studied themselves. The labour market is now full of these crops of students that cannot perform of their own volition coupled with unemployment saga in the nation. As a result, most graduates have now resolved to look for alternatives to survival through yahoo-yahoo; book-haram etc. which have affected security atmosphere in schools and colleges and the country at large (Bello, 2012).

The concept of Managing Education for Security

Managing education for security in the promotion of the development of education in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa is an indispensable tool in the hand of educational administrators. The weapon of innovation is used to sustain hitch-free atmosphere in the school system to achieve education objectives. Anyawu (2019) carried out research on the best factors to maintain adequate security in school organization and she reported that improper management of the education system in terms of resource allocation, corruption, and poor leadership corruption is albatross to national development in Nigeria. Most importantly, emphasis on vocation and technical education to inculcate in the student's skills of self-reliance that will take them off the street and away from social crime-related behavior that inhibits adequate maintenance of security in school environment for smooth administration are not implemented well.

At present, there is existence of threats against security in schools in the like of activities of gunmen, bandits, kidnappers, book-haram/ISWAP who occasionally and without notice endangered the security virtues of citadel of learning most especially at basic and post-basic institutions today (Bello, 2012). A number of students have been denied their fundamental human right of free access to education; equity and fair play. The instance of Chibok girls; etc. are living witness to attack against the peace of the colleges due to insecurity challenges that are prevalent in the country up till now.

Security education entails the mechanism put in place by school organizations through the enabling instrument in the policy by the government to avoid, or ameliorate, prevent, or resolve violence through conflicts, and threats that originated from people, other states, non-state actors, or structural socio-political and economic conditions in the community, state, or nation. Nwagboso, (2012) stipulated security terminology as the act of being safe from harm or danger, the defense, protection and preservation of values, and the absence of threats to lives and properties. Security as a concept is all about survival and the condition of human existence to enjoy maximum safety wherever. This development exists when people live together in a certain environment without disturbance or violence. In the same vein, Adejumo (2011), mentioned that security is the act of keeping peace within the governing territories. This is usually done by upholding the national law and defending the internal security threats in different areas of the country, this time around in school organisations. Adebakin, (2012) also viewed security as freedom from danger or threats, and the ability of a nation to protect and develop itself, promote and cherish values and legitimate interests and enhance the well-being of its citizenry.

Likely Innovative Educative/ Programme in the Education Policy formulation for National Development.

The federal government through relevant organs and agencies have established the following statutory bodies as channels of innovation. There was a placement for such in the National Policy of Education, FRN, (2014) and Universal Basic Education Act of 2004 (UBEC, 2008).

1. **Universal Basic Education of 6-3-3-4.** This was created to bring about free education and entrepreneurial and vocation education for innovation of self-reliance and not book knowledge. Students are to spend six years in primary school; three years in junior secondary school; three years in senior secondary schools and four years in tertiary institutions (Universal Basic Education Commission, 2008). This system of education translated into 9-3-4 unimplemented in the year 2009; and now 1-6-3-3-4 structure of practice (UBEC, 2008). The system of education was backed up by Universal Basic Education Act of 2004 with stated laudable objectives that could lead to innovation and security for educational development.
2. **Educational Management Information Systems:** This aspect was packaged by the Federal Ministry of Education and the support of relevant agencies like United Nation International Children Education Fund, etc. to gather data on every form of school activity and process them to become information for the aid of easy decision making in the sector. Necessary information on students' enrolment; repeating rate; graduation rate; promotion rate among others will be got with minimum effort of the operators. This may promote innovation as well
3. **Technical Education:** This aspect of education policy programme encourages technical education after secondary education. According to FRN, 2014, technical education is offered in universities, mono technics, polytechnics, Colleges of Education (Technical) and other specialized institutions. The courses of study

include woodwork; welding; artwork; catering and hotel management and a host of others. As of today, there are limited technical schools around. The goals of technical education in the policy basically if well implemented reflected innovation for development in the sector. Such include among others, exposure to professional studies in the technologies; training people who can apply scientific knowledge to solve environmental problems for the convenience of mankind; training that imparts the necessary skills for the production technicians, Technologists and other skilled personnel who shall be enterprising and self-reliant among others (FRN, 2014). All these put together may be an agent of innovation in schools for development and security.

Challenges of Managing Education for Innovation and Security in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa

Policy formulation and implementation have a series of challenges in managing education for innovation and security in the development of education in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa. This came as a result of a missing link between the government and the public user of policy and also the government and its agencies when fail policy during implementation stage when addressing the reasons why it was not successfully implemented. Dahida and Peter postulated the following as challenges of managing education for innovation and security.

1. Multiplicity of agencies involved
2. Lack of or inadequate coordination among the players
3. Bureaucratic orders of actors regarding when agencies could implement the policy with what terms.
4. The duration of the programme to promote continuity as planned.
5. Corruption in the systems of formulation and implementation of the policy by stakeholders
6. Lack of continuity in government policies.
7. Inadequate human and non-human resources sometimes.

All these put together created gaps between stated policy, goals, and the realization of such as planned initially (Makinde, 2016).

Conclusion

The paper concluded among others that, education policy blueprint may not actually be the issue in its formulation as there are inputs and statements for a particular level of educational administration that possesses elements of innovation for security education and development in the sub-Saharan Africa. It is the ability and capability of stakeholders to identify such areas of innovation for development in the programme and then implement the policy to achieve objective. Several educational policy structures/programmes such as 6-3-3-4; 9-3-4 in 2009; and now 1-6-3-3-4 curriculum have been implemented.

The examination of trade and vocational education subjects in 6-3-3-4 could be seen as a package to bring about innovation for security education. The challenges of these programmes include personnel; funding; capacity building of staff; supervision of programme of studies; infrastructures among others during curriculum implementation (Harbau & Egbebi, 2019). More so, there are about 35 trade subjects in the Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, (2014) which promote entrepreneurial education for learners. Constraints against all these are equipment and material for the teaching and practice of all these (Dahida & Peter, 2013).

If students should choose agriculture, there ought to be farmlands provided by schools and trained teachers to teach and guide the students to become mechanized farmers. As a result, the problem may not be with the education policy formulation but the implementation strategies and plans that will bring about innovation for security education. Insecurity abounds today in most schools, most especially in the Northern part of Nigeria. Most students are not in schools, the case in point of the almajeris; some learners are out of school. Devil usually finds jobs for idle hands and it is the categories of these out-of-school children that will grow up to become Boko-haram, bandits, gunmen, and many more. The Chibok girl in Maiduguri and Dasi experience are reference points in which so many learners were abducted and taken away as security threats to school administration and educational development in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The federal, state, and local government education authorities in the 774 local government areas of Nigeria as part of sub-Saharan Africa countries should get a unique pattern of implementing educational programmes according to the dictate of the policy. For instance, consider innovation of educational management information systems: materials and necessary resources should be provided by all in the process of implementation.

The goal of Universal Basic Education as an innovation should be to promote self-reliance of learners. Such students should be followed by the teachers to letter to acquire skills, knowledge and competence in that discipline e.g. manufacturing of dormy motor vehicle. A learner who is good in technology should be identified, taught, encouraged, and monitored to become a self-motivated student to manufacture a machine for the advancement of the economic development of the nation.

Physical objects on which innovative ideas are required in schools should be supplied to all schools in the right order and not that students should be learning theoretical values in abstract in the four walls of classrooms. Some equipment that was imported by some Unity Party of Nigeria government in the year 1983 melted away in schools.

Teachers to bring about innovative ideas in the school curriculum for security education as a matter of compulsion should be adequately sent abroad for training on the know-how of teaching such subjects in the four walls of classrooms.

The three levels of governance in the country vis a vis the federal, state, and local government must partner with private investors including Non-governmental organizations to bring in all stakeholders during planning and implementation of school curriculum for innovation and security education. This is because the fact that outlay on education is enormous and cannot be single-handedly figured out by the government alone due to higher school population.

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